

What follows are the standard operating procedures (SOPs) that were used during the NOAA RESTORE Science funded project “Fire Effects in Gulf of Mexico Marshes – Historical Perspectives, Management, and Monitoring of Mottled Ducks and Black and Yellow Rails” from 2029-2026.

These are provided to document our procedures, for questions please reach out to Auriel Fournier (auriel@illinois.edu)

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Mottled Duck Monitoring Standard Operating Procedures

NOAA Firebird Project

Version 3.0 (February 2022)

Description

We are surveying for breeding Mottled Ducks in high marsh across Texas, Louisiana, Mississippi, and Alabama to better understand how prescribed fire in those wetlands impacts these birds. These surveys will be done from elevated platforms looking for different types of Mottled Duck flight behaviors.

Safety

NOAA Firebird Project Priorities

1 - Human Safety, 2 - Bird Safety, 3 - Equipment Safety, 4 - Data Collection.

Human Safety - Survey should not be completed during hazardous weather (thunder/lightning). Those traveling by boat to sites will wear life jackets as appropriate whenever on a moving boat. When traveling by boat, a float plan should be completed and filed with at least one person, located on the mainland, who will serve as the primary contact should an emergency occur. Float plans should include, at a minimum, contact phone numbers and emergency contacts for all persons on the boat, launch location, description, including license plate number, of the vehicle used to pull the boat/trailer and expected return time, etc. Each survey team should carry at least one cell phone with them for emergency communication. Field radios will be carried when available and dispatch is available. A first aid kit will be available/kept in each vehicle and boat. If at any time a person doing fieldwork feels unsafe continuing, they get to say so, and fieldwork stops, be that person a volunteer, a field tech, or a PI. No one will be punished for making the safe choice.

Equipment

- Binoculars (recommended 8X42 or better)
- Elevated platform - tower/ladder
- Cell phone or tablet with Avenza maps loaded with call survey points OR GPS Unit, with appropriate maps loaded, and Batteries
- Clipboard/sheet holder
- Field Datasheets, on *Rite-in-the-Rain* paper
- Kestrel Wind Meter
- Writing Utensil - #2 lead pencil (including pencil sharpener or extra leads if using mechanical pencil) or *Rite-in-the-Rain* waterproof pen
- Sighting (Mirrored) Compass
- Rangefinder
- Snake chaps where appropriate (Turtleskins brand works well)

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Procedures

Pre-Survey Tasks

Load GPS Points/Avenza

Charge Batteries or have spare batteries

Survey Tasks

From February-July these observations will be done in the morning (i.e., 30 minutes before sunrise to 3 hrs after sunrise) or in the evening (i.e., 90 minutes before sunset to 30 minutes after sunset). Each survey will be conducted for 10 minutes at each survey location. Each point will be revisited at least 6 times during the season, with a goal of 3 morning and 3 evening surveys when logistically feasible. Survey points will be spaced a minimum of 1000 m apart.

Mottled duck surveys may be conducted concurrent with BLRA surveys for a field crew of two (combined species surveys for paired observers). The survey will be conducted with one member of the field crew focusing on the BLRA survey and the other on the MODU survey. Surveyors should focus solely on one species and not assist each other during the survey. Observers will be randomly assigned (flip coin) to each species per route.

For a field crew of one, combined species surveys for solo observers: this involves sequential and alternating mottled duck and rail broadcast surveys. If this survey methodology is used, observers should alternate which species is surveyed first (e.g., first survey point- conduct mottled duck survey first ten minutes and rail second ten minutes; second survey point- conduct black rail survey first ten minutes and mottled duck second ten minutes, third point- same sequence as survey point one).

MODU surveyors will arrive at the site either by boat, on foot, or by truck. Upon arrival at the survey sampling, they should set up an elevated observation platform at 4-5 feet above ground level. The observation platform may be a ladder, a truck bed, UTV bed, altered retriever platform, etc.. The observer should be able to stand on the elevated observation platform and scan (360 degrees) the surrounding area without concern for tipping over. The observer should continually and consistently scan the surrounding area with the naked eye and binoculars to a distance of up to 500 m. Record a GPS coordinate of the elevated platform. If combined with BLRA surveys, the platform should be located 5-20 m from the location where BLRA surveys are conducted to avoid obstruction of sound during call back surveys.

When a surveyor observes a pair or individual MODU, they should immediately estimate and record the estimated distance and bearing to where the bird(s) were detected. It is especially important to take a bearing and distance to MODU locations if observed entering or leaving vegetation (e.g., possible nest).

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For drop flights, the surveyors should immediately estimate and record the distance and bearing to the drop location (i.e., where the bird(s) disappeared down into the vegetation). Further, they should also record the minute during the survey when the drop (i.e., the birds disappeared into the vegetation) occurred.

For chase flights, record every minute of the survey when the flight was observed.

Record environmental data once a survey period at the beginning of each sampling period.

For vegetation surveys associated with mottled duck locations, priority should be given to first detection locations, over multiple detections at a single location (i.e., more points across the landscape vs higher frequency of points at a single survey location).

For more details on different MODU behaviors please refer to this [powerpoint built by Joe Lancaster](#).

Post-Survey Tasks

After field work is complete for a given survey period and field crews have returned to their lab or lodging site, the data recorded on the Breeding MODU point count survey data sheet should be entered into the Firebird database (see Firebird data entry reference guide for information regarding data entry). Ideally this should be done on the same day that the data were collected. Once data are entered into the Firebird database, the surveyor should scan, photocopy, or take pictures of the data sheets and email them to Peter Kappes (pk565@msstate.edu).

References

If this protocol needs to be changed/updated, please contact Auriel Fournier (auriel@illinois.edu; 419.307.6261)

Breeding Rail Monitoring Standard Operating Procedures

NOAA Firebird Project

Version 4.0 (last updated June 2 2022)

Description

We are surveying for breeding Black Rails in high marsh across the five U.S. Gulf of Mexico states to better understand how these birds respond to prescribed fire in Gulf Coast tidal wetlands. These surveys will be done using call-broadcast point count surveys.

Safety

NOAA Firebird Project Priorities

1 - Human Safety, 2 - Bird Safety, 3 - Equipment Safety, 4 - Data Collection.

Human Safety - Those traveling by boat to sites will wear life jackets as appropriate whenever on a moving boat. A first aid kit will be kept in the vehicle/boat. When traveling by boat, a float plan should be completed and filed with at least one person, located on the mainland, who will serve as the primary contact should an emergency occur. Float plans should include, at a minimum, contact phone numbers and emergency contacts for all persons on the boat, launch location, description, including license plate number, of the vehicle used to pull the boat/trailer and expected return time, etc. If at any time any person doing field work feels unsafe continuing, they get to say so, and field work stops, be that person a volunteer, a field tech, or a PI. No one will be punished for making the safe choice.

Bird Safety - Care should be taken while doing call-broadcast and when leaving a point to ensure that birds which may have approached the surveyor are not stepped upon.

Equipment

- [FOXPRO NX4](#) - Use a sound meter to determine the volume setting for each call playback file is between 80 and 90 db measured at one meter from the speaker. Make a mark on the unit so that it can be easily reset there for future use. Because there are several calls on each call playback make sure that at least one of them is ~90 db.
 - *This make/model is no longer available, we are working on an alternative*
- Cell phone/tablet with Avenza maps & points OR GPS Unit with points and batteries
- Clipboard/sheet holder
- Field Datasheets, on *Rite-in-the-Rain* paper
- Kestrel Wind Meter
- Writing Utensil - #2 lead pencil (including pencil sharpener or extra leads if using mechanical pencil) or *Rite-in-the-Rain* waterproof pen
- Sighting (Mirrored) Compass
- Rangefinder
- Binoculars
- Snake chaps where appropriate (Turtleskins brand works well)

Survey Conditions

Surveys will not be conducted when the wind is above 20 km/hr or when sustained precipitation can be clearly felt on the surveyor's face (i.e., drizzle). If you arrive at a survey point and it is unsafe to conduct the survey at that location (e.g., poison ivy, disturbing nesting birds, alligator nest) determine if you can move the point to a nearby location that doesn't violate the distance requirement and removes the threat and conduct survey there. Be sure to document this in the comments of the datasheet and record the lat/long of the new site. If it is impossible to relocate the site, drop it and let your supervisor/crew lead know so they can replace it.

Procedures

Pre-Survey Tasks

One time

Test Call-broadcast system to be sure it is adequately charged for the survey period (or that there are sufficient replacement batteries) and determine the volume level that results in 80-90db 1 meter from the speaker each day.

Everytime

Charge batteries and/or bring spare batteries

Songs loaded

Points in GPS (in decimal degrees) or Avenza Maps

Compass

Enter the lunar phase on datasheets prior to heading into the field

[\(timeanddate.com/moon/phases/\)](http://timeanddate.com/moon/phases/)

Survey Tasks

From 15 March – 31 July black rail call-broadcast point count surveys will be done in the morning (i.e., 1 hour before sunrise to 3 hours after sunrise) or in the evening (i.e., 90 minutes before sunset to 1 hour after sunset; sunrise-sunset.org/). Depending on whether the survey is being conducted in the morning or evening, every effort should be made to initiate call playback surveys at the beginning of the survey window to take advantage of the full window.

BLRA call-broadcast surveys may be conducted concurrent with MODU surveys for field crew of 2 (see below 2-person survey). For one person surveys where BLRA and MODU surveys are being completed and where logistically feasible, whether BLRA or MODU survey is done first should be alternated.

Each BLRA survey will be conducted for 10 minutes at each point count point. Point count points will be a minimum of 500 meters apart. Each survey point will be surveyed 6 times during the season.

Call-broadcast sequence is: 2 min passive - 30 sec of calls - 2 min passive - 30 sec of calls - 2 min passive - 30 sec of calls - 2.5 min passive (TOTAL = 10 minutes). After the 1 minute place

marker is heard, start recording data. Whether or not a BLRA is detected should be recorded in 30 second blocks.

If the observer is unsure if they heard a BLRA that should also be recorded with a line on the datasheet with a note made about what the observer thinks they have heard.

When a BLRA is detected, the surveyor should use the rangefinder to estimate the straight-line distance from their location to the bird's estimated position to the nearest meter and record the bearing of the bird using a sighting compass (which is not declinated).

1-person survey

On arriving at the point count point, place the speaker 3m to the NE of the point so that it is oriented to broadcast to the widest extent of habitat (recording the bearing) at a standard height of 120 cm and horizontal to the ground. The surveyor should stand at the point. During the call-broadcast period, the surveyor should stand in place for the duration of the count but may turn in place to listen/look for birds in all directions. When a BLRA is detected the surveyors should estimate the straight-line distance to a detected bird from their standing location.

Prior to initiating the BLRA point count, the surveyors should record the wind speed and sky condition (percent cloud cover to the nearest ten percent). If the observer is standing in the wetland, water depth should be recorded at the point where the observer is standing. If the observer is standing on a road or levee, then water depth should be measured twice, 10 meters into the wetland vegetation perpendicular from either side of the road/levee. If there is no standing water it should be recorded whether the ground is dry, or moist. Lunar phase data should be collected prior to entering the field. The surveyor should face due N to start the survey but rotate in place throughout the call-broadcast point count survey period to ensure adequate coverage of the entire survey area.

2-person survey

Same as above, allowing the MODU surveyor to set up their equipment prior to initiating survey. Be sure to time initiation to coincide with the MODU survey. If the second person is NOT surveying for MODUs they should conduct a separate BLRA survey (i.e., 2 independent BLRA surveys being conducted at the same time). A critical assumption of a double survey like this is that the 2 surveys are completely independent. Under no circumstances should either observer cue off of the other observer or alter their observations due to the other observer or ensuing discussions. It is completely okay to have different observations! Do NOT coordinate your data or discuss if you detected responses or not with the other surveyor and do your best not to be influenced by them recording data. In an effort to reduce the potential influence of one observer influencing the other, be sure to enter any observation data in real time OR a "0" in each observation bin (if nothing is detected) after it is completed.

The second surveyor should stand 3 m 45° SE of the call-broadcast speaker.

Post-Survey Tasks

When the survey is completed record the background noise using the following codes 0 = no noise; 1 = faint noise; 2 = moderate noise (probably cannot hear a BLRA beyond 100m during >30 seconds of the survey); 3 = loud noise (probably cannot hear a BLRA beyond 50m during >30 seconds of the survey); 4 = intense noise (probably cannot hear a BLRA beyond 25m during >30 seconds of the survey).

After completing all surveys for the day, use the site (localconditions.com) to record the barometric pressure in the region when you performed the survey. You can click on the “View More Charts” option to view a chart with the pressure trends. Record the barometric pressure at the start of the surveys and the trend in pressure during the time you conducted the surveys. Please convert from inHg to mmHg.

Data Collection and Measurement Descriptions

Prior to beginning each survey for the day, record the day, month, and year at the top of the data sheet. Write down the name of the surveyor, the lunar phase coded on a scale of 0 (= day of new moon with no moon light) to day 15 (full moon). Days 14 to 1 reflect the progressive decrease in moonlight during waning and, inversely, days 1 to 14 reflect the progressive increase in moonlight during waxing (Spear et al. 1999) (timeanddate.com/moon/phases/). In instances where the waning numbers would mean a new moon is a non-zero number on the day of a new moon, the 0 for the new moon should be used instead, and the waxing numbers started on the following day.

Water depth can be classified as dry, saturated, or measured in centimeters if there is standing water. Water depth = saturated if when a person’s finger is pushed into the ground one inch, and pulled out there any amount of water fills the depression within 15 seconds.

Sky condition should be measured to the nearest 10%.

Use the Kestrel to record the starting temperature (°C) and wind speed (km/h; set the unit to the average wind speed function, point into the wind and record for 30 seconds). Enter the start time of the survey OR time of detection if not during a call-broadcast survey (military time).

When individual BLRAs are detected, write “1” in the appropriate time column if the BLRA was heard, “S” if seen, and “1S” if both heard and seen. Enter data for each new BLRA you hear during the call broadcast on a new line (i.e., the number of rows will correspond to the number of individual BLRAs detected). The first time you hear a “new” individual BLRA use the rangefinder to estimate the distance the bird was from the surveyor and the compass to determine the bearing of where the rail was detected. If you believe the bird in that row of the dataset was detected at the previous point, indicate that in the previous point column. At the end of the survey, write in the notes for each individual detected which calls you heard from that individual: *kic-kic-kerr* (KKR); *growl* (GRR), *churt* (CHR), or *ink-ink-ink-ink* (INK).

Call File Description

Call-broadcast sequence is: 2 min passive - 30 sec of calls - 2 min passive - 30 sec of calls - 2 min passive - 30 sec of calls - 2.5 min passive (TOTAL = 10 minutes). After the 1 minute place marker is heard, start recording data. Whether or not a BLRA is detected should be recorded in 30 second blocks.

At 0 seconds has "Start"

Has 30, 1, 130, 3, 330, 4, 530, 6, 630, 8, 830, 9, 930 (all seconds) at those time intervals to help with data collection in the field

Has 10 seconds of kickydoo, 10 seconds of growl, and 10 seconds of churt (in that order; total of 30 seconds) at 2, 5, and 7 minutes

At 10 minutes has "End"

Incidental Detections

Each observation of BLRA is valuable, even when they are encountered outside of surveys. When observing a BLRA outside of the formal surveys, those detections should also be recorded. If you are unsure about a detection, please still record it, along with notes about what you did observe. Do not use call broadcast, phishing or any other method to try and get further response from an individual to confirm identification.

When an individual is detected outside of surveys, take a GPS point of where the observer was when the bird was detected. Also record the bearing and estimated distance to the individual. In the notes report whether the detection is for sure, or only possible, whether it is visual and/or auditory, and if auditory if the bird was heard once or multiple times, and what call type(s) you heard.

If this protocol needs to be changed/updated, contact Auriel (auriel@illinois.edu)

Description

We are surveying for Black Rails and Yellow Rails during the winter (November-February) in high marsh habitats across the 5 US Gulf of Mexico states to better understand how prescribed fire in those wetlands impacts these birds. These surveys will be done with draglines, at night. Dragline surveys can be completed without captures, but regardless of whether or not captures are occurring, anytime a dragline survey is done someone who is named on the take permit must be present supervising the survey.

Critical Definitions:

- Site - the broad descriptor of an officially designated area, such as a National Wildlife Refuge, State Wildlife Management Area, conservation area, or research reserve where sampling is taking place
- Experimental Unit - the local area of interest within a site where a specific management treatment is applied
- Route - a collection, often a linear string, of nearby sampling plots/points that can be sampled in consecutive order in a given sampling period (i.e., a morning or evening sampling period)
- Vegetation Plot - plots centered on random points, or points where black rails have been detected
- Point Count Point - the geographic point, including an exact latitude-longitude, where a breeding Black Rail call-broadcast point count, and/or a Mottled Duck point count is conducted
- Surveyor - the person(s) conducting and recording data associated with the breeding Black Rail and/or Mottled Duck point count surveys
- Dragline Plot - A 170x170m plot (or area of different dimensions by 28900 m² if habitat does not allow a 170x170 plot). This plot will allow for parallel passes of the 15 m wide dragline with ~ 2 meter space between passes, to be completed in a 3 hour period
- Lunar Phase - recorded at the beginning of the survey. Use codes 0-15 - from the protocol: 0 (day of new moon with no moon light) to day 15 (full moon). Days 14 to 1 reflect the progressive decrease in moonlight during waning and, inversely, days 1 to 14 reflect the progressive increase in moonlight during waxing.

Safety

NOAA Firebird Project Priorities

1 - Human Safety, 2 - Bird Safety, 3 - Equipment Safety, 4 - Data Collection.

Human Safety - Each person will have a headlamp, and waterproof boots and be dressed for the weather. One member of the group will carry a first aid kit during the survey. Everyone needs to carry drinking water with them, and at least one cell phone should be carried for

emergencies. Surveys will be limited to 3 hours per night, to help limit fatigue and ensure safe decision making for the people and the birds. Breaks should be taken every 45 minutes or so to check in on group members. In areas where rattlesnakes may be encountered, snake chaps

should be worn (Turtleskin brand are effective and a bit lighter than other brands). If at any time a person doing field work feels unsafe continuing, they get to say so, and field work stops, be that person a volunteer, a field tech, or a PI. No one will be punished for making the safe choice.

Bird Safety

- We will follow the instructions from here for how to capture individuals:
<https://www.fws.gov/southeast/pdf/guidelines/banding-conditions-for-eastern-black-rail.pdf>
- We are making our draglines with plastic bottles, with rounded edges, with weights inside, to help reduce potential risk to birds.
- Not all states will likely capture Yellow Rails, that decision will be made by the state lead, but those which do should collect samples (feathers, fecal, photos) in the same way they are done for Black rails
- Black Rails will ONLY be captured by TRAINED project staff who are named on the take permit. Volunteers are allowed to assist in the pulling of the dragline. With training and specific permission from the master bander a volunteer may be allowed to capture Yellow Rails.
- Banding equipment should be carried into the field, so the bird can be banded near its capture location.
- When approaching an area where a bird is located, NEVER run. Feet should be shuffled, to reduce risk of stepping on the bird. Never attempt to capture a bird that is flying, as this will likely result in mortalities or injuries to the bird.
- The large dip-net should be carefully placed over the bird when visible, and not thrown down over or near the bird. The net should not be used to probe vegetation or drive out birds who are hidden.
- Birds will be held post capture, pre-banding in paper lunch bags. Bags will not be reused.
- Do not handle birds if you have a non-natural insect repellent on your hands (i.e., ones containing DEET)
- Processing time (bird actually being handled; i.e., not in the bag but being held in the hand) should be ≤ 5 minutes, including the time it takes for taking pictures
- The vast majority of the time the entire team will stop draglinning to process a captured bird. Only in instances where there are two named people on the take permit present, can those not involved in the banding continue the dragline survey while the bird is processed.
- Holding time in a bird bag should be ≤ 60 minutes
- Hand warmer can be stored inside holding bag to help keep bird warm if necessary

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- ALL bird bags containing a bird will ALWAYS be held by a person from the dragline team that remains stationary next to the bander and NEVER be laid on the ground, banding box, portable chairs, table, etc.
 - See [project photograph rules](#) for specific details on bird and field work photography
 - If at any time during the holding or handling period the bird exhibits ANY sign of STRESS (e.g., puffing of body feathers, head drooping, panting, or lethargy) the bird should be released IMMEDIATELY.
-

Equipment

DRAGLINE

- Parachute cord, with 8 plastic bottles evenly spaced along the 15 meter length.
- 4 bottles will contain bells and 4 will contain cat toys; 10 bells/toys in each bottle
- Each end of the dragline will have a 10-12cm pvc handle for pulling dragline

HEADLAMPS

- Headlamps must have a MINIMUM power of 210 lumens and a MINIMUM life of 6 hours of burn time

GPS

- A handheld GPS unit that can collect a track, and updates that track at least every 10 seconds.

HAND-HELD SPOTLIGHTS

- Should be hand-held
- Each dragline survey team should have ≥ 4 hand-helds spotlights.
- Spotlights must have a MINIMUM power of 1000 lumens and a MINIMUM life of 6-8 hours
- At the user's discretion, a lanyard or other cord can be attached to the spotlight to help keep the spotlight from falling into standing water during use.

FOR CAPTURES

Scale - electronic balance with 0.1-g precision, NOT a Pesola or similar handheld scale

Bands

Banding Pliers

Band Removal Pliers

Bird Bags for Holding Birds

Measuring devices for body measurements

Camera for photos

[Nets](#) - recommend a 20 inch rim, with a fin ($< \frac{1}{2}$ inch) mesh, and a bag at least 18 inches deep. A non-collapsible net if possible will hold up better over time.

Coin envelopes for feather storage.

FOR FECAL COLLECTION

Microcentrifuge tube
Sterile swabs
70% ethanol solution

Survey Conditions

Surveys will not be conducted when the wind is above 20 km/hr, or when temperatures are below 40F, or when it is raining more than a mist.

Dragline surveys begin 30 minutes after sunset, and surveys will be limited to 3 hours per night, to help limit fatigue and ensure safe decision making for the people and the birds.

Procedures

Pre-Survey Tasks

Assemble Team - No more than 8 people participate in a dragline, and at least 4 people are required. With four people behind the line, and the others if present on the sides.

Capture materials should always be carried by a member of the team, in case Black Rails are encountered.

Batteries charged - Headlamps, Spotlights

Site Boundary Loaded - The outline of the 170x170m plot should be delineated ahead of time in GIS or GPS software and made visible on the gps unit, so the survey coordinator can ensure that the group stays within the correct area.

FOR CAPTURES - Bird Bags cleaned, batteries for scale

Data Collection and Measurement Descriptions

Prior to beginning each survey for the day, record the day, month, and year at the top of the data sheet. Write down names of group members.

The lunar phase coded on a scale of 0 (= day of new moon with no moon light) to day 15 (full moon). Days 14 to 1 reflect the progressive decrease in moonlight during waning and, inversely, days 1 to 14 reflect the progressive increase in moonlight during waxing (Spear et al. 1999) (timeanddate.com/moon/phases/). In instances where the waning numbers would mean a new moon is a non-zero number on the day of a new moon, the 0 for the new moon should be used instead, and the waxing numbers started on the following day.

Sky condition should be measured to the nearest 10%.

Use the Kestrel to record the starting temperature (°C) and wind speed (km/h; set the unit to the average wind speed function, point into the wind and record for 30 seconds). Enter the start time of the survey OR time of detection if not during a call-broadcast survey (military time).

Record Barometric Pressure (mmHg) and indicate trend (rising, falling, steady).

Survey Tasks

Turn on GPS Track

The track of the dragline will be maintained and recorded using a handheld GPS. With the survey coordinator, devoting their attention to the GPS and ensuring that the line does not wander. Often it is most helpful to have this person be one of the two people pulling the rope, so they can take a more active role in redirecting the line as needed. For each survey, the survey coordinator will use the GPS tracking feature to record the exact path of the survey within each survey plot.

The dragline will be pulled in a serpentine pattern to complete 10 passes across the survey area (Figure A).

Universe of 2.89-ha plot dimensions, assuming a 15-m rope, and 2-m gap between transects

Width (m)	Length (m)	N Passes
17	1700	1

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	34	850	2
51	567	3	
68	425	4	
85	340	5	
102	283	6	
119	243	7	
136	213	8	
153	189	9	
170	170	10	

Dragline surveys should be done at walking speed, such that each member is able to walk easily at that pace for a long period, and no one is out of breath (<1 mile/hour).

The observers on each end of the line drag it slowly through the area of interest, while shifting it back and forth horizontally.

Crews should consist of no less than 4 people evenly spaced along the line. Observers at the ends of the line should look ahead and to their side, looking closely for rails, while dragging the line and maintaining a slight “u” formation. Additional observers may walk approximately 2 meters behind the line, and should be watching the area immediately around the line and in the body of the “u” behind those dragging the line for moving rails. This lessens the likelihood of overlooked birds but also decreases the chance that an observer will collide with or trample a bird.

The bottle line technique functions by disturbing black rails, causing them to move through the vegetation that provides them with overhead cover. They may not emerge for capture, so observers must learn to spot movements of vegetation indicating the presence of a moving black rail. Black rails may sometimes resemble mice with their movements, as they may “wiggle” through the vegetation. In addition, observers should learn to identify the bird in flight because they can flush from the vegetation and make brief flights before resuming cover. Often the rail will emerge from vegetation and move across it, and this is the time when observers

may capture the bird using a capture net (see Figure 1 below). It is important to recognize that not all rails will emerge from vegetation and that banding crews may not be able to spot a bird for safe capture though they can see it moving in the vegetation. In this event, they will have to refrain from capture attempts. Attempting to confine and capture a rail that is not completely visible may result in mortality or injury to the bird. Do NOT use the capture net to probe the vegetation, as any disturbance to birds that are not visible may also result in mortality or injury to the bird.

FOR CAPTURES

When a Black or Yellow Rail is flushed, a predetermined person stays with the dragline, and records the time the line stopped and started, to aid in clipping out the transect coverage area from the GPS track after the fact. A GPS point will be recorded at the location the bird was first observed. When a bird is captured, it will be taken 20 feet behind the dragline to reduce further disturbance to the bird. If multiple birds are captured at the same time, the people holding birds in bags should remain stationary, by the bander so that the next bird is always available for processing and that no bird injuries result from accidental falls by the people holding bags. By remaining stationary during bird banding, team members will also limit habitat impacts to the banding site. After the banding process is completed, stow all banding supplies and have all people assisting the bander return to the dragline. Prior to releasing the bird, it is the banders responsibility to insure that the route to be followed on the dragline will NOT pass over the release site. Once this is confirmed the bander can release the bird at the banding location (i.e., 20 ft behind the dragline).

The GPS Point will be named to collect the associated data about the point.

`AAAY001`

AAA = three letter plot ID

Y = Y or B, depending on bird species

001 = three digit number of birds captured that night.

Post-Survey Tasks

Daily (the day after survey)

Download tracks from GPS

Label tracks according to naming scheme, clip for start/end time

Enter data on track length, time surveyed, etc,

Download Points

Run R script on points file to extract data from point names.

Add site name to the point file.

Download Photos

Label photos using this naming convention

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'1111-11111_YYYY_MM_DD_type'

Where 1111-11111 is the band number

YYYY is the four digit year

MM is the month

DD is the date

Type is the photo type (headside, bodyside, bodyback, bodyfront, wing)

For those who don't have internet access, excel sheets will be provided by Auriel Fournier with rule sets built in to aid in data entry. For those who do have internet access, instructions will be provided by Auriel Fournier on how to enter data into the database.

Once data are entered, spreadsheets should be sent to Auriel Fournier along with scans of all datasheets, the gps track files, and the photos.

Send banding data to the master permit holder so that it can be submitted to BBL (contact master permit holder for your state for details)

Measurement Descriptions

FOR CAPTURES

Species

Weight - Birds should be weighed to 0.1g with some sort of electronic balance, NOT a Pesola or similar handheld scale. Birds can be placed on the scale in the bag, and the bag weighed after release to determine the bird's weight.

Unflattened wing cord (to +/- 0.5 mm) - Best to have a thin ruler with a perpendicular stop at zero. The ruler should be inserted under the wing, and the bend of the wing should be pressed snugly against the stop. Do not apply any more pressure than needed to secure the bend, you should not be depressing the wing. Once the wing is in place, make sure that the line between the carpal joint and the tip of the longest primary lies parallel to the edge of the ruler. Align the ruler so it touches the longest primary, and read the measurement (modified from Pyle Vol 1).

Tarsus (to +/- 0.5 mm) This measurement will be taken with calipers. It is the length between the intertarsal joint and the distal end of the last leg scale before the toes emerge.

Sex

Female (left) - more white on throat
Male (right) - little to no white on throat

Female; wing <82
 Usually bolder dark eye
 patch, narrower supercilium

Male; wing >82
 Usually paler
 broader supercilium

Age

New, "adult-like"
 feathers

Retained juvenile
 feathers

Rallids follow either a Complex Basic or Complex Alternate Strategy

- All have a preformative molt
- Some have a prealternate molt

The preformative molt is partial or incomplete

- Usually molt limits among the alulas
- Usually molt limits between greater and primary coverts
- Sometimes molt limits among the greater coverts
- Molt limits in tertials hard to see
- Juvenile inner secondaries (e.g., s5) often more pointed than in adults

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Formative (HY), sex unknown
Yellow Rail - Oct

Definitive Basic (AHY), sex unknown
Yellow Rail - Oct

Yellow Rail - Nov
Formative (HY), sex unknown

Fallacies in Pyle (2008) for Yellow & Black Rails

- The amount of white in the secondaries is not an aging criterion for YERA
- The extent of the preformative molt is not as limited as depicted
- YERA do their fall molt on the breeding and non-breeding grounds
- P10 spotting in Black Rails is a useful, but not reliable criterion

Photos

- First photo taken should be of something containing the bird's band number and date.
- Head shot from the side

- Full body shot from the side
- Full body shot from the back, including tail
- Full body shot from the front, including throat, breast, and as much of belly as possible

- Fully extended wing - be sure wing is spread such that one can clearly see all four alula feathers, greater coverts are visible; **STRONGLY** suggested wing photos be taken using a flash (cover birds eyes)

- Last photo taken should be of something containing the bird's band number and date.

Feather collection details -

Feathers should only be collected by those who have received appropriate training, as determined by the master permit holders.

For each rail, the first secondary feather should be gently pulled from a secured wing, and then secured in a coin envelope. The coin envelope should have the bird's band number, the date, and the GPS coordinate name of the capture location.

Fecal Collection details -

Fecal samples will be collected from each rail captured.

Fecal sample collection will use the protocol described by Knutie and Gotanda (2018; Figure 5), **without** the protective grate. Place the modified weigh boat at the bottom of the bird bag. After birds have been captured in the field, place them in the paper bag for 3-5 minutes, which is how long it takes most birds to defecate after being captured. If handling time would exceed 20 minutes overall the time in the paper bag waiting for defecation will be skipped, as bird time from capture to release must be <20 minutes.

After removing the bird from the bag, carefully remove the weight boat. Bend the weight boat into a funnel shape and place the narrow end in a microcentrifuge tube. Use the sterile swabs to move the feces into the tube, and then remove the end of the swab and place that into the tube, as well. Cover the fecal sample and swab in 70% ethanol solution and label the tube with the band number of the bird that left the sample. Place the labeled tube in a labeled coin envelope.

A new weigh boat should be used for each sample.

Figure 5. This figure shows materials used to collect fecal samples.

Winter Rail Monitoring/Capture/Banding Standard Operating Procedures
NOAA Firebird Project
Version 1.5 (last update July 26 2023)

Store all samples in a safe place (ideally refrigerated or frozen) and once the collection season is completed send all samples to

Dr. Chris Butler
Dept. of Biology
Box 89
University of Central Oklahoma
100 N University Drive
Edmond, OK 73034

If this protocol needs to be updated, contact Auriel (auriel@illinois.edu; 419.307.6261)

Standard Operating Procedures
NOAA Firebird Project
Version 5.1 (last updated November 17 2022)

Vegetation Sampling SOP

We are measuring the vegetation of wetlands that are being surveyed for birds so that we can understand the response of the vegetation to the prescribed fire management, and also bird abundance or occupancy.

Safety

NOAA Firebird Project Priorities

1 - Human Safety, 2 - Bird Safety, 3 - Equipment Safety, 4 - Data Collection.

Human Safety - Care should be taken to ensure that people are not collecting data during hazardous weather conditions (afternoons on very hot days, during thunderstorms, etc). Those traveling by boat to sites will wear life jackets as appropriate whenever on a moving boat. A first aid kit will be kept in the vehicle/boat. When traveling by boat, a float plan should be completed and filed with at least one person, located on the mainland, who will serve as the primary contact should an emergency occur. Float plans should include, at a minimum, contact phone numbers and emergency contacts for all persons on the boat, launch location, description, including license plate number, of the vehicle used to pull the boat/trailer and expected return time, etc. For sites where venomous snakes are present, snake chaps should be worn. If at any time a person doing fieldwork feels unsafe continuing, they get to say so, and fieldwork stops, be that person a volunteer, a field tech, or a PI. No one will be punished for making a safe choice.

Black Rail Nest Safety Eastern black rails emit the nest defense diversion call ("tch-tch-tch" in Conway 2011, "ink-ink-ink" according to Sibley guides) when people approach within several meters of an active nest. Whenever encountering this, crews shall assume that they are within several meters of an active BLRA nest. Crews will not approach the BLRA or attempt to locate the nest, but will record a gps coordinate with estimated distance and bearing instead and leave the area immediately using the same route they used to approach the coordinates. Crews will not return to attempt sampling for 3 weeks past that date. Crews will observe a 50-m radius buffer around the gps coordinates for all activities within the sampling area until 3 weeks have passed. Crews will be provided auditory examples of this distress call so that they are able to identify it.

Crews will be trained to recognize BLRA chirps and growl calls, so that they are aware of vocalizing individuals in close proximity to them. Crews will not attempt to approach vocalizing birds or engage them, and should be observant of the potential for tended chicks to be present whenever they hear these calls. When traveling through vegetated habitats, they will walk slowly, listen for these vocalizations, be vigilant for broods in transit, and carefully move away from broods if observed. Vegetation plots will not be set up and sampled to encompass stationary broods if present. However, crews may sample vegetation the same day if they hear chirps or growls or kee calls but are given no indication that stationary broods or active nests are present within their intended vegetation plot.

Equipment

- First aid kit
- Sunglasses or safety goggles to prevent eye injury from juncus
- Cell phone or tablet with Avenza maps loaded with call survey points OR GPS Unit, with appropriate maps loaded and Batteries
- Clipboard sheet holders
- Field datasheets on *Rite-in-the-rain* paper
- Writing utensil- #2 lead pencil (including pencil sharpener or extra leads) or *Rite-in-the-rain* waterproof pen
- Light gloves (some veg can be sharp and/or pokey)
- Sighting (mirrored) compass
- Grass clippers of choice (pruners, shears, saw, weed eater with brush blade attachment)
- Robel Pole
 - A two-meter tall, half-inch PVC pipe, with 10 cm increments marked along its length in alternating black and white strips. A rope or cord of 4 meters in length should also be attached halfway up the Robel pole. This should be accompanied by a meter stick, to aid the observer in being far enough away, and at the right height for observation.
- Quadrat (25 cm incorporated into 50 cm quadrat)
 - 3-sided PVC quadrat, ½ meter to a side, with the connection piece divided into 2, 25 cm segments, forming a “W” or “M”. For transport, a rope or elastic can be run through the pieces, to allow them to be broken down and set back up more easily.
- Disc pasture meter
 - A ¾ inch thick disc 12 inches in diameter, with a ¾ inch hole in the center. All discs should weigh 1 kg. A one-meter tall ½ inch PVC pipe is marked with 1 cm marks along its length and is inserted through the center.

Procedures

Selecting Vegetation Plot Locations

Google Earth:

Open Google Earth (GE) and set the Lat/Long to decimal degrees (Tools > 3D View tab > Show Lat/Long > radio box Decimal Degrees click Apply). Then navigate to the location of your call broadcast survey (breeding season) or rope drag unit (non-breeding season). For the non-breeding surveys you can either import a geo-referenced polygon file or shapefile of a polygon of the rope drag survey area. Denote the furthest extent of your survey area in the 4 cardinal directions or top/bottom and left/right (e.g. N/top: 30.334705; W/left: -89.239557; E/right: -89.236572; S/bottom: 30.330756).

Using your web browser, navigate to the Zonum Solutions online KML-Toolbox and the “KML-Random Points” tool (<http://www.zonums.com/> > KML-Toolbox > KML-Random Points). Once there, enter the number of random points you wish to generate (we’ll be selecting 5 locations for each rope drag polygon during the non-breeding season), extents of your survey area, and set the elevation to 0 (see figure below). Then click generate points. The tool will look like it has frozen saying “Wait, generating random points...” Ignore the message and click on “Download KML File”, which will download a KML file of your random points. Navigate to wherever you store your web downloads and double-click the

file to open the random points in GE. Because many of our survey areas are not perfect rectangles, make sure that ALL of the random points fall within the boundaries of the survey area. If one or more fall outside of the area, repeat, saving points until you have the number you need to satisfy the SOP for whichever season you're generating points for. These will be the locations where you will set up your vegetation plots.

Once you have the Lat/Long for the vegetation plots be sure to enter their Lat/Long information into the Firebird database using the Locations data entry form. You can get the Lat/Long information by right clicking on the point in GE. Once you have the a lat/long information for your vegetation site, be sure to assign each plot an ID using the following convention:

XX(state)-XXXX(site)-XXXX(route)-VEGE(survey type)-###(number)

(e.g., MS-HANC-BACA-VEGE-001; HANC = Hancock Co. Marsh Coastal Preserve; BACA = Bayou Caddy area; VEGE = vegetation survey; 001 = plot number 1).

Survey Tasks

The vegetation data collected is the same, regardless of the season or point type (random or place where a bird was detected). DO NOT perform vegetation surveys if there is standing water > 5cm in depth over more than 1/4 of the plot. Come back and sample when there is less/no standing water and you can see where vegetation is entering the ground. If your vegetation plot (or point) falls within a patch of poison ivy adjust the measurement such that it avoids the poison ivy and document what you did to relocate it (e.g. large stand of poison ivy on measurement point 5, moved the measurement to the east to avoid). If the plot falls such that it would negatively impact a nesting bird, move the plot such that sampling no longer impacts nesting birds and notate how the plot was relocated. Data should be collected in the following order to minimize disturbance to the vegetation. Use the codes found in table 1 at the end of this document when identifying vegetation to species.

Plot = the 18m radius circle

Subsample = the place where measurements (see below) C-F are taken

Subsample 1,2,3 and 4 are each 10 m from the central point in the 4 cardinal directions

Subsample 5 is 5 meters from the central point to the NE

Subsample 6 is 15 meters from the central point to the SW

Measurements

A. Habitat Type from the central point - Entire plot

- B. Visual Estimation for Percent Cover from the central point - Entire plot
 - a. At the data collectors discretion this could be collected last if exploring the plot while doing the sub sample would help with this estimation.
- C. Quadrat for Percent Canopy Cover - once in each subsample
- D. Robel Pole for Visual Obstruction - once in each subsample
- E. Disc Pasture for Duff Layer - once in each subsample
- F. Clip plot - once in each subsample

Habitat Type from the central point

Stand at the center of the sample plot and classify the dominant (>50% of the cover) habitat type into one of the following categories (see below). The habitat classes and descriptions are from the SHARP avian point-count circle - [Plant Communities and Habitats protocol/datasheet](#) and Correll et al. (2018)

Low Marsh

- Regularly flooded by daily tides
- Dominated by tall form *Spartina alterniflora* (50+ cm/20+ in) or *Spartina cynosuroides*

High Marsh

- Flooded only by greater than mean high tide
- Often dominated by *Spartina patens*, *Distichlis spicata*, *Spartina spartinae*
- Includes areas of short form *Spartina alterniflora* (1 - 35 cm/0.4 - 14 in) as well as *Juncus roemerianus*, *Scirpus pungens*, *Scirpus robustus*, *Limonium nashii*, *Aster tenuifolius*, and *Triglochin maritimum*

Salt pools/pannes

- Depressed, bare areas with sparse vegetation cover and extremely high soil salinities. Generally, pools retain water between high tides while pannes do not.

Terrestrial Border

- Area infrequently flooded by storm and spring tides and can include areas of marsh with fresh/brackish water due to a high water table and/or runoff from impervious surfaces.
- Most common: *Typha angustifolia*, *Iva frutescens*, *Scirpus robustus*, *Baccharis halimifolia*, *Solidago sempervirens*, *Panicum virgatum*, and *Spartina pectinata*

Phragmites

- The various forms (genotypes) of *Phragmites australis*.

Mudflat

- Exposed muddy areas free of vegetation.

Open Water

- Larger areas of water such as bays, channels, rivers, ponds.

Upland

- All non-marsh terrestrial cover, which includes non-marsh land uses that could either be natural (e.g., agriculture, pasture, grassland) or developed.

Beach

- Areas of open sandy ground.

Visual Estimation for Percent Cover from the central point

While standing at the center of the plot, visually estimate the % coverage of the different plant species with a minimum of $\geq 5\%$ coverage within the plot (the area within the 18 m radius circle around the point). Dead vegetation should be recorded as its own separate category but does not include vegetation that is on the ground and decomposing. Include water if the plot has $\geq 5\%$ open water and wrack categorized as either tidal or hurricane wrack if $\geq 5\%$. If you are sampling during the wintertime, senescent herbaceous plants are “living” and should be identified to species. Percent cover of salt pannes and bare ground should also be separately recorded if either is $>5\%$. The estimate may not sum to 100% if for instance there is 60% juncus, 35% bare ground and 5% a mixture of other things, you would not record the mixture of other things.

How to locate the sub sample location

The robel pole can be used to estimate distance from the central point to the sub sample points while walking in a straight line from the central point. The central point is located with a GPS unit.

Quadrat for percent canopy cover

Slide the quadrat along the ground and into place, doing your best place the subsample location at the set distance from the central point. The missing side of the quadrat allows this to be done without flattening vegetation. Look at the 50 cm X 50 cm quadrat from above, and estimate, to the closest 5%, what percentage of the ground is covered by vegetation, not including dead vegetation.

Robel Pole for Visual Obstruction

For visual obstruction, readings will be taken at a distance of 4 meters 90° to the east of the robel pole, such that the surveyor's eyes are at a height of 1 meter above the ground. Starting at the ground, scan up until you can see the robel pole, and record which stripe is first visible (e.g. if the first 3 intervals are completely obscured and a portion of the fourth interval is partially visible, record 40 cm).

For someone working solo, bring a piece of rebar to stick in the ground and keep the rebar upright when you step away the 4 meters distance.

Disc pasture for duff layer

Hold the PVC rod perpendicular to the ground, with the bottom of the blue weighted disc 1.5 m (marked by an orange band of tape) above the ground level. Then release the disc and allow it to drop under its own weight. Record the settling height of the disc by placing your fingers on the pole at the top of the disc apparatus. Pull the pole out of the disc and use the meter stick to measure from the bottom of the pole to the surveyor's fingers.

Clip plots

Once the location of the clip plot has been identified, place the quadrat on that point. Use the outline of the 25 X 25 cm quadrat (highlighted with red on the PVC) to delineate the boundaries of the clip plot. Use a hand tool to trim the area within the 25 X 25 cm quadrat to 3" (~8 cm) above ground level. The clippings from the plot will not be kept. Now assess the % coverage of the plot by estimating

coverage to the nearest 5%.

Post-Survey Tasks

Ideally data should be entered on the day it is collected but at least once a week. Enter the data into the Firebird database using the Vegetation form (see Firebird data entry reference guide for information regarding data entry). Once data is entered, scan, photocopy, or take pictures of the data sheets and send them to Auriel Fournier. For those without internet access, data will be entered into the excel sheet provided by Auriel Fournier, with built-in rule sets to help catch data entry errors quickly. Each time data entry is completed, the excel sheet, and scans/photos of the paper datasheets will be sent to Auriel Fournier for incorporation into the project-wide database.

Calculating clip plot % cover: It is up to the discretion of the state leads whether to have the technicians run the script to calculate % cover, but it is recommended that whoever is responsible for this is familiar with R. The script to calculate the % cover of vegetation can be found on the Firebird Google Drive [here](#):

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1RmhNSabfvT1t45PfczcoBa-tmZf9oGip/view?usp=sharing>. Before running the script be sure to place all of the “traced” images into the same folder and make that your working directory. After you run the script there will be a new folder in your working directory named “countColors_output”. In that folder you’ll find your “processed” pictures, which should have the “filled” areas changed to cyan. You will also find a .csv file named “CalculatedClipPlotResults” in that folder, which contains the name of the image file with another 2 columns that have the percentage of the image that is covered by vegetation. Be sure to provide this information to your technicians to add these values to the corresponding datasheet(s) or add them yourself, and make sure that they get entered into the database.

References

Correll M.D., Hantson, W., Hodman, T.P., Cline, B.B., Elphick, C.S., Shriver, W.G., Tymkiw, E.L., and Olsen, B.J., 2018, Fine-Scale Mapping of Coastal Plant Communities in the Northeastern USA: Wetlands v. 39, p. 17- 28, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13157-018-1028-3>.

If this protocol needs to be changed/updated, please contact Auriel Fournier (auriel@illinois.edu; 419.307.6261).

Table 1.

USGS codes, and common and scientific names of plants commonly found in high marsh habitat along the Gulf Coast. (<https://plants.usda.gov/home>)

USGS code	Common name	Scientific name
MYCE	Wax myrtle	<i>Myrica</i> (<i>Morella</i>) <i>cerifera</i>
BAHA	Baccharis or Sea myrtle	<i>Baccharis</i> <i>halimifolia</i>
IVFR	Marsh elder	<i>Iva frutescens</i>
SPAL	Smooth cordgrass	<i>Spartina</i> <i>alterniflora</i> (<i>Sporobolus</i> <i>alterniflorus</i>)
SPPA	Salt-meadow cordgrass	<i>Spartina</i> <i>patens</i> (<i>Sporobolus</i> <i>pumilus</i>)
SPSP	Gulf cordgrass	<i>Spartina</i> <i>spartinae</i>
JURO	Black or needle rush	<i>Juncus</i> <i>roemerianus</i>
DISP	Salt grass	<i>Distichlis</i> <i>spicata</i>
ANGL	Bushy bluestem	<i>Andropogon</i> <i>glomeratus</i>
PAVI	Switch or panic grass	<i>Panicum</i> <i>virgatum</i>
CLMA	Saw or cut-grass	<i>Cladium</i> <i>mariscus</i>
BAMA	Saltwort/Batis	<i>Batis maritima</i>
BOFR	Sea oxeye	<i>Borrchia</i>

	daisy	<i>frutescens</i>
TYLA	Broadleaf cattail	<i>Typha latifolia</i>
SABI	Annual glasswort	<i>Salicornia bigelovii</i>
SAVI	Perennial glasswort	<i>Salicornia virginica (depressa)</i>
SCAM	Three-square bulrush	<i>Schoenoplectus americanus (olneyi)</i>
SCRO	Seacoast bulrush	<i>Schoenoplectus (Bolboschoenus) robustus</i>
ILVO	Yaupon holly	<i>Ilex vomitoria</i>
PEBO	Redbay	<i>Persea borbonia</i>
PEPA	Swamp bay	<i>Persea palustris</i>
MOLI	Shore grass	<i>Monanthochloe littoralis</i>
SADE	Virginia glasswort	<i>Salicornia depressa</i>

USGS Code	Common name	Scientific name	Seen in only this state
ALPH	Alligator Weed	Alternanthera	TX

		philoxeroides	
AMAR	Sandhill amaranth	Amaranthus arenicola	
AMPS	Cuman ragweed	Ambrosia psilostachya	
ANAR	Scarlet Pimpernel	Anagallis arvensis	TX
ANGL2	Bushy bluestem	Andropogon glomeratus	
ANVI4	Green silkyscale	Anthenantia villosa	?
AVGE	Black mangrove	Avicennia germinans	FL
BACOP	Waterhyssop	Bacopa sp.	TX
BAHA	Eastern baccharis	Baccharis halimifolia	
BAMA5	Turtleweed	Batis maritima	
BOFR	Sea oxeye daisy	Borrichia frutescens	
BOLBO	Bulrush	Bolboschoenus sp.	TX
BREAKWATER			
CAGL5	Southern Waxy Sedge	Carex glaucescens	MSAL
CALO5	Long's sedge	Carex longii	MSAL
CAREX	Sedge	Carex sp.	TX

CASEA	Casearia		FL?
CEER2	Erect Spadeleaf	Centella erecta	TX
CIRSI	Thistle	Cirsium sp.	TX
CLMA10	Saw or cut-grass	Cladium mariscus	
COAR	Florida silver palm	Coccothrinax argentata	MSAL
CYDA	Bermudagrass	Cynodon dactylon	TX
DEAD	Dead plants		
DEPA6	Panicled-leaf ticktrefoil	Desmodium paniculatum	LA
DISP	Salt grass	Distichlis spicata	
DIVI3	Virginia Buttonweed	Diodia virginiana	TX
ELOB2	Blunt spikerush	Eleocharis obtusa	
ELEOC	Spikerush	Eleocharis sp.	TX
FISP	Fringe rush?	Fimbristylis sp.	hot spring fimbry? but that is FITH...what about hurricane grass FICY in FL
FICA3	Carolina Fimbry	Fimbristylis castanea	MSAL
GATI	Stiff marsh	Galium tinctorium	MSAL

	bedstraw		
GAPU	Indian Blanket	Gaillardia pulchella	
GROUND	Bare ground/mud		
HYBO	Largeleaf pennywort	Hydrocotyle bonariensis	
ILVO	Yaupon holly	Ilex vomitoria	
IMCY	Cogonrass	Imperata cylindrica	MSAL
IVFR	Jesuit's bark	Iva frutescens	
JUEF	Common Rush	Juncus effusus	TX
JUNCU	Rush	Juncus sp.	TX
JURO	Black or needle rush	Juncus roemerianus	
JUVA2	Roundhead Rush	Juncus validus	TX
LEERS	Cutgrass	Leersia	TX
LEMI3	Common duckweed	Lemna minor	MSAL
LIPU2	Prairie Dogshade	Limnoscium pumilum	TX
LUGR9	Large-flower primrose-willow	Ludwigia grandiflora	TX

LYCA2	Carolina desert-thorn	Lycium carolinianum	
LYLI2	Wand lythrum	Lythrum lineare	MSAL
MicroForb			TX
MIMOS	Sensitive plant	Mimosa sp.	TX
MOLI	Shoregrass	Monanthochloe littoralis	
MOCE2	Wax myrtle	Myrica (Morella) cerifera	
NOBI2	Crowpoison	Nothoscordum bivalve	TX
PANO2	Bahiagrass	Paspalum notatum	
PARE3	Torpedograss	Panicum repens	
PARE3	Torpedograss	Panicum repens	TX
PASPA2	Crowngrass	Paspalum sp.	TX; LA
PAVI2	Switch or panic grass	Panicum virgatum	
PEBO	Redbay	Persea borbonia	
PEPA37	Swamp bay	Persea palustris	
PHAU7	Common reed	Phragmites australis	

PHCA6	Carolina Canarygrass	Phalaris caroliniana	TX
PHAM3	American Pokeweed	Phytolacca americana	MSAL
PHNO2	Turkey tangle fogfruit	Phyla nodiflora	LA
PIEL	Slash Pine	Pinus elliottii	MSAL
PIPA2	Long Leaf Pine	Pinus palustris	MSAL
PLANT	Plantain	Plantago sp.	TX
POSA5	Arrowleaf tearthumb	Polygonum sagittatum	MSAL
RUTR	Southern Dewberry	Rubus trivialis	MSAL
SABI	Annual glasswort	Salicornia bigelovii	
SANIC4	American Black Elderberry	Sambucus canadensis	MSAL
SACA3	Texas-star, Prairie rose-gentian	Sabatia campestris	TX
SADE10	Virginia glasswort	Salicornia depressa	same as SADE10 TX
SAGRA	Hogwood	Sagraea sp.	FL

SALA	Common arrowhead	Sagittaria latifolia	FL; SALA is Sagittaria lancifolia can't find Sagittaria latifolia
SARU			MSAL
SAST5	Rose of Plymouth	Sabatia stellaris	MSAL
SADE10	Virginia glasswort	Salicornia virginica (depressa)	
SCAM	Three-square bulrush	Schoenoplectus americanus (olneyi)	Originally SCOL...USDA says is SCAM
SCCY	Woolgrass	Scirpus cyperinus	FL
SCLA14	Common clubrush	Schoenoplectus lacustris	LA
SCPUL4	Common threesquare	Schoenoplectus pungens var. longispicatus	TX
BORO5	Seacoast bulrush	Schoenoplectus (Bolboschoenus) robustus	
SOCA6	Canada Goldenrod	Solidago canadensis	MSAL
SOME3	Seaside Goldenrod	Solidago mexicana	MSAL
SOSEM	Seaside goldenrod	Solidago sempervirens	

SPAL	Smooth cordgrass	Spartina alterniflora (Sporobolus alterniflorus)	
SPART	Cordgrass	Spartina	TX
SPCY	Big Cordgrass	Spartina Cynosuriodes	MSAL
SPPA	Salt-meadow cordgrass	Spartina patens (Sporobolus pumilus)	
SPSP	Gulf cordgrass	Spartina spartinae	
SPVI3	Seashore dropseed	Sporobolus virginicus	FL
STHE9	Amberique-bean	Strophostyles helvola	
TRSE9	Chinese tallow	Triadica sebifera	MS/AL
TYLA	Broadleaf cattail	Typha latifolia	
UNPL	Unknown/unidenti fied plant		
DISC3	Velvet panicum	Dicanthelium scoparium	
VICIA	Vetch	Vicia sp.	TX
WATER	Water		
WRACK	Wrack		

NOAA Firebird Project Priorities

1 - Human Safety, 2 - Bird Safety, 3 - Equipment Safety, 4 - Data Collection.

How we represent ourselves as professionals, and our project, is very important to the public's perception of our profession, and the success of our project. This includes the photos/videos we take, and the context we share them in.

Photo/Video Rules

These rules include traditional photograph/videography, and any capture of images or video for use in apps such as snapchat, tiktok, instagram or other mediums of sharing photos or videos. If you have questions, ask.

When taking photos of yourself, or others, ensure that you are all doing things which are safe, legal, and permitted. Including the wearing of appropriate safety equipment (life jackets when on boats, snake chaps when in rattlesnake habitat, etc). If you are not, fix your behavior immediately, and make changes to ensure those things don't happen again in the future, photographs or not.

When taking photos/video, ensure that you have any kind of geotagging turned off, to prevent folks who may wish to find these places either because of enthusiasm for the birds, or to do them harm, from doing so.

Photographs of birds in the hand for personal purposes are considered the lowest priority and taken only when the bird shows no signs of stress and when time and safety allows. When taking photos of birds in the hand, permission to take photographs must be obtained from the bander-in-charge, who can revoke that permission at any time. All photography equipment should be prepared before the bird is placed in anything other than the bander's grip. Birds will be held in the photographer's grip for no more than 60 seconds. Photos will not be allowed on any bird which is showing any sign of distress. We are not holding birds for more than 60 minutes, this includes banding, and photographs, there will be no exceptions. If flash must be used, it would be best to ensure that the bird's eyes have time to adjust before it is released.

Only those who are trained and whose training has been approved by the state lead (Texas = Warren Conway, Louisiana = Erik Johnson, Mississippi/Alabama = Mark Woodrey, Florida = Jim Cox) are allowed to hold birds, including for photographs, at the discretion of the bander in charge. For project techs and other staff who are not able to handle birds, a bird could be held close to them by an off frame person to allow a photo with the bird. Photographs of visitors holding birds should be discouraged, but at the discretion of the bander in charge, photographs of visitors helping to release birds may be allowed.

Sharing photos/video

You are welcome to share project photos/videos with your friends and family via social media and other means, as long as those photos and video are in compliance with these rules.

When sharing photos of birds in the hand, you are required to include in the caption “This/These bird(s) were captured and handled as part of a scientific research project, and under the authorization of federal and state permits, and university ethics review, and were released unharmed immediately after.”

Do not geotag your photos at anything finer than the county/parish scale, these are species of conservation concern, and we do not want over enthusiastic members of the public, or those with more harmful intentions to find these birds because of our photos.

Do not share any photos or videos that contain other people without their explicit permission.

Always be sure to review the audio paired with any video collected to ensure it is appropriate.

Location Sharing

You are not permitted to share the location of Black Rails with anyone outside of the project, for any reason without specific permission from the state lead (Texas = Warren Conway or Jena Moon, Louisiana = Jonathan Lucek or Erik Johnson, Mississippi/Alabama = Peter Kappes or Mark Woodrey, Florida = Heather Levy or Jim Cox).

eBird or other publicly available records

To protect the location of Black Rails, an federally listed species, from those who might harm the birds or their habitats through malice or misplaced enthusiasm, every checklist that is submitted when working or volunteering on the project must be submitted as a hidden list, no exceptions. Those lists can be shared with others who were present. Similar policy for submission of any sightings to iNaturalist, or other similar platforms. This rule is in place regardless of whether or not you have seen a Black or Yellow Rail on that given day. If you don't know how to submit a hidden lists please ask before submitting anything to eBird or other platforms.

How to make a hidden checklist on eBird:

Wait to submit your checklist until you are at a computer so that you can hide it as soon as possible after you submit it. Do NOT share your checklist until you have completed the following and have hidden it. Complete your checklist as you would any other (e.g., incidental, travelling, how many people, etc.). Immediately after submitting your checklist go to eBird on your computer and open the checklist you

Photo, Video, Location Sharing, eBird Rules
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wish to hide. Look for the blue “Checklist tools” box in the upper right corner and select “Hide from eBird output” from the drop down menu (see Figure below).

Edit date and effort

96319, -90.15261 Jefferson Parish, Louisiana, United States Edit location

Checklist tools

1 Species observed 1 individuals

1 Red-tailed Hawk *Buteo jamaicensis*

CHECKLIST FLAGGED
Hidden checklist. This checklist has been hidden from public view by the owner of the checklist: this checklist and its observations are only visible to the checklist owner and do not appear in public eBird outputs. More information.

Hide from eBird output

Once you select that option you will get a notification that selecting this option will hide your checklist from eBird output, which is what we want. Select the Green “Hide Checklist” button. Once you have done that you will see a note on the left side of the checklist indicating that the Checklist is Flagged as hidden (red box in Figure above). At this point, you can share the checklist if you need to. You’re done!